

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR FORMING SUGGESTOPEDIC SKILLS IN FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *In the new conditions of social development, the idea of future educators, the nature and content of professional training are changing. The person-oriented paradigm of education sets the future educator the task of teaching technologies that will allow the child's individuality and skills to be fully developed.*

Keywords: *suggestopedic, modernization, pedagogical technologies, thoughts on education, moral qualities, pedagogical correction.*

Recently, the problems of modernization of the educational system, adaptation of its methodological structure and search for effective educational technologies have become especially relevant. This is related to the changes taking place in the life of the country - the strengthening of negative trends in the economy, social sphere, culture and education, the prevention of the weakening of the pedagogical environment of the preschool education organization in relation to the growing negative social phenomena. A new system was created in this field in accordance with the decree "On measures to fundamentally improve the management of the education system" and the decree "On organizing the activities of the Ministry of Pre-School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan". In this regard, the role and importance of the future educator's professional literacy and skills, his ethics and moral qualities, and the sense of responsibility for the consequences of his activity are increasing significantly. The objective condition for the modernization of higher education as a social institution is implemented in accordance with the Convention on the Rights of the Child, the Law "On Education" and the concept of modernization of education.

In the new conditions of social development, the idea of future educators, the nature and content of professional training are changing. The person-oriented paradigm of education sets the future educator the task of teaching technologies that will allow the child's individuality and skills to be fully developed. State requirements for the content and level of training of a qualified graduate in the department of the mandatory minimum content of the professional education program in psychological and pedagogical sciences, assimilation of knowledge based on the basic pedagogical technologies imposed on the graduate of the preschool education field, it is also necessary to have a technique based on suggestopedic skills, which is carried out by influencing the unconscious area of the child's psyche.

It should be noted that the science of preschool pedagogy for the first time turned into the need to consider the pedagogical possibilities of suggestopedia and its implementation in educational practice, the problems of absorbing influence were deeply and comprehensively developed in the works of physiologists, sociologists and psychologists. Concepts of the suggestopedic mechanism were created (I.P. Pavlov, I.M. Sechenov, V.M. Bekhterev, A.F. Lazursky, S.L. Rubinshtein, A.A. Bodalev, K.I. Platonov, V.N. Myasishchev, A.M. Svyadoshch). Suggestopedia is considered as a factor of interaction of people in the process of communication and activity (V.A. Bakeev, A.G. Kovalyov, V.N. Kulikov, A.V. Petrovsky, K.K. Platonov, B.F. Porshnev, etc.) Works analyzing the important role of suggestopedia in the process in pedagogy

(Guyo, V.M. Bekhterev, P.P. Blonsky, S.V. Kravkov, A.S. Makarenko). issues of using self-hypnosis in the system of self-education of future educators were developed (I.E. Shvarts, L.V. Gasheva, A.S. Novoselova, B.K. Moiseev, Z.A. Cherepanova, etc.).

All of the above studies allowed us to distinguish the problem of formation of suggestopedic skills from the point of view of modern achievements of science, and at the same time show the description of suggestopedia without taking into account the history and theory of the suggestopedic phenomenon.

Suggestopedia summarizes the work on learning from different perspectives, and we determined its generalized descriptions.

Table 1.1

The main features of Suggestopedia

physiology	tablet	sociology
“suggestopedia is the most simplified typical conditioned human reflex”	“is to provide information that has a relevant impact on the course of the processes”	“suggestopedia is an indestructible –primary phenomenon, the main fact of human mental life”; “suggestopedia (social contagion) is the relatively rapid, unconscious, and irrational spread of any mood, impulse, or behavior”

Despite clear evidence of the importance of suggestopedia as a method of influencing a person, a vague attitude to this problem has been formed in the science of pedagogy. Most official textbooks on pedagogy either ignored suggestopedia as a method of influence or mentioned it in passing, or described it as a method of manipulating the mind and arousing the passions.

B.T. Likhachev in his article “Ecopsychotherapeutic Aspects of Education” describes education and training as “not only external influence, but also the process of gradual self-mastery, coordination of conscious actions and unconscious motives” in the formation of personality recognizes that it is important not only in the conscious realm but also in the unconscious. The author refers to methods related to suggestopedia as means of accessing the unconscious.

B.T. Likhachev gives the following definition of suggestopedia:

“As a method of influence, suggestopedia is a method of manipulating children's minds. It is used to arouse passions, install thoughts and images, distract, suppress emotions, frighten, morally elevate a person or it is achieved through psychological means such as discrimination, overestimation or underestimation of his physical and mental strengths”.

Such a radical change in the above point of view can be explained by a number of reasons:

1. The concept of “suggestopedia” is associated with an omnipotent, universal means of influencing the consciousness of a person in everyday life.
2. Traditionally, persuasion is considered the main method of educating a conscious person.
3. The concepts of “persuasion”, “indoctrination”, “influence” and “suggestopedia” are often defined.

There is a sufficient amount of psychological and pedagogical research that proves the legality and necessity of using this method of influencing a person for educational purposes. The modern direction of social development tells us about the need for suggestopedic skills in the service of pedagogical sciences and practice in order to humanely form a person and protect him from the negative influences that modern society is so rich in.

Several stages can be distinguished in the history of studying the pedagogical possibilities of suggestopedia:

1st stage - work that is a necessary condition for creating the foundations of the theory of suggestopedia;

2nd stage - monographs devoted to the study of suggestopedia and its role in education;

3rd stage - the work of tutors and professors (characteristics of suggestopedia and conditions of its use);

4th stage - researches of modern authors that form the basis of the theory of suggestopedia and its application in the pedagogical process.

One of the authors, Juvansiy, in his work "On the influence of the teacher" considers various methods of pedagogical influence and their effectiveness. Instead of threats and punishments, "it is better to frequently inspire future educators with ideas about the benefits and pleasures associated with oral sciences". In order to solve this problem, the professor-teacher should know each future educator, his doubts, weaknesses and strengths, gain the confidence of the future educator without realizing it, and have an imperceptible influence on his worldview.

Without distinguishing two more types of influence - imitation and suggestopedia, the professor-teacher of the English language of the 17th century. John Locke describes these two phenomena in his Thoughts on Education. Reflecting on the most effective influences in education, he emphasizes that the simplest, most convenient and effective of all methods of forming the character of children is to set before their eyes examples of what to do and how to do it.

At the end of the 19th century, as a result of research in the field of the psychology of suggestopedia, the first serious monographs appeared on the role of suggestopedia in education. M. Guyot was the first to develop and justify a number of rules related to the theory of suggestopedia: the importance of management for the implementation of suggestopedia; connection of suggestopedia with persuasion; the need to receive and share ideas to be inspired by others; the strength of suggestopedia depends on tone of voice, which enhances facial expressions.

In his works of N.A. Dobrolyubov talks about suggestopedia and the negative side of influence. Since the basis of all his pedagogical considerations is the idea of individual sovereignty, independence, independence, he considers giving the child the right to "conscious action" as an indispensable condition of education. Dobrolyubov in his work "On the Importance of Authority in Education" points to the need to educate an independent-thinking child who cannot withstand the advice of the older generation. If the child obeys orders with which he does not agree, and they inspire him to obey, not reason, he obeys and gradually develops blind obedience to authority. The child loses confidence in his own mind, loses courage and strength in his thinking, is afraid to form his own opinion and does not dare to act on his convictions.

Therefore, the unconditional obedience caused by constant suggestopedias kills the independence of the mind in the child and has a harmful effect on the emotions. The ability not to be a puppet in the hands of others, to follow their aspirations, allows the child to realize himself as a unique and unique person. Suppressing the child's will until he gets used to unconditional obedience also affects his attitude towards the teacher. He (the child) becomes nervous and insecure. The habit of unconditional obedience (which corresponds to a high level of innate or developed suggestopedia) affects the formation of the will. "Educators should show more respect for human nature, try to develop, not suppress, the inner world of future educators, and education should strive to make a person moral, not by coercion, but by consciousness and confidence".

Considering the possibility of using suggestopedia in education, V.M. Bekhterev noted the extraordinary impressionability of children, which leads to a high level of suggestopedia.

However, from the scientist's point of view, "individuals who are not susceptible to external influences should be created, not individuals who can be "suggestopediated" through education".

Also V.M. Bekhterev considered the role of suggestopedia in education, which, according to him, consists of the influence of: the environment; people around; educator; teaching method.

S.V. Kravkov's monograph "Suggestopedia (psychology and pedagogy of suggestopedia)" (1924) is dedicated to the study of the psychology of suggestopedia and its role in the pedagogical process. He emphasizes that the psychological nature of suggestopedia is important considering the possibility of using it in pedagogy. In his work, S.V. Kravkov notes that there are several ways to implement pedagogical suggestopedia. It is the educator's thoughts, views, statements, likes and dislikes. But the absorbing effect of the example is particularly great. Since any moralization is more abstract, an example, a visual representation, as an opportunity to make a specific and emotionally vivid pedagogical demand, turns out to be the most effective in this case. This, according to the scientist, explains the dependence of children's moral concepts and ideals on the people around them, which is determined by high imitation and suggestopedia in childhood. "The influence of what is perceived in the early years of life is often the background, the perspective, from which we approach life".

Analyzing the positive and negative effects of Suggestopedia, S.V. Kravkov notes the following:

- suggestopedic skill has a depersonalizing effect, educates the character that defines each person;
- if suggestopedic skills are developed, then the criticality of perception decreases, and therefore, a person is exposed to any absorbing influence, including negative content;
- the experience accumulated by a person as a result of absorbing influence is illogical, unconscious, and the suggestopediated person cannot dispose of it.

Several counterarguments can be made to these considerations.

1. Since the result of the absorbing effect depends on its content, it depends on the person who organized the suggestopedia to emphasize or depersonalize the individuality of the future educator.

2. The very position about the development of recommendation skills raises doubts. According to, the research of many authors, including S.V. Kravkov they suggestopedic skills are more or less specific to each person and can decrease or increase depending on different life conditions. Therefore, it is not recommended to purposefully increase suggestopedia, which really leads to the consequences that the scientist pointed out.

3. If the content taught to the child does not bear fruit in practical life or the child's life conditions do not contribute to it, then suggestopedia loses its power.

Among the positive features of using Suggestopedia, S.V. Kravkov names the following:

- imitation, that is, a suggestopedic skill, helps the child and it is much easier to acquire culture;
- all suggestopedias made unconsciously are logically based on actions, in which case they become part of life experience controlled by consciousness;
- with the help of suggestopedia, it is possible to develop the qualities of criticality and thoughtfulness of a person in relation to the environment

If the suggestopedic skill, as a normal feature of the human psyche, is not used for pedagogically valid purposes, it (suggestopedicity) can become a tool in the wrong hands, which

is often pedagogically harmful.

Well-known defectologist V.P.Kashchenko in his "Pedagogical correction", considers suggestopedia as a method of correcting deviations in the development of children's personality, distinguishing between awakening and hypnosis. The scientist defines suggestopedia as "one of the important factors of "absorbing" normal character traits that affect the child and are acceptable in his current and future social activities". According to him, the conditions under which this method can be used are interesting: the value of the educator's personality in the eyes of the future educator, knowledge of character defects that need to be corrected; sympathy and trust from the child to the educator; possession of the discourse necessary to implement suggestopedia. Then the scientist unwittingly emphasizes the importance of suggestopedic skills and emphasizes that "the atmosphere at home, the general tone of the surrounding relatives and teachers - everything affects in one way or another the process of the formation of a person". Children are highly imitative and are influenced by all the factors of life around them.

The scientist convincingly proves that specially organized procedures and events have an educational effect, as well as the environment in which a growing person develops. Therefore, it is important for everyone involved in education to know certain pedagogical rules and postulates and to master different methods of education and to keep in mind the property of the child's soul. Absorbing everything around - and above all, caring about the purity of their own thoughts and actions, it is no less, and sometimes more inspiring. Therefore, according to the scientist, the teacher's constant work on himself, self-education, and improvement of his spiritual and moral qualities become an indispensable condition for the implementation of suggestopedia.

In the works of A.S. Makarenko, "Methods of organizing the educational process", "Lectures on raising children" also emphasize the need to use suggestopedia along with other methods of education. He notes that the share of suggestopedia is in demand, which must be expressed in a firm, "hard" voice. But it is impossible to make unreasonable, vague, demands that are not related to real life necessity. Testing requirements will not be met anyway, and even if they are met, it will affect the administration of the professor. Suggestopedia means that the future educator must have the necessary skills to control the child's face, voice and face in order to fulfill the requirement.

The next most important stage of the study of pedagogical possibilities corresponds to the middle of the 60s - the beginning of the 70s. During this period, research was conducted in several areas.

1. To study the mechanism of relaxation therapy and the possibilities of its application in the educational process (suggestopedia laboratory I.E. Schwartz).
2. development of the suggestopediaopedic method of intensive teaching and a number of serious studies of scientists in this field based on it (S.N. Kitaigorodskaya).
3. Defining and justifying the system of medical pedagogy of Dr. A.A. Dubrovsky.
4. Research in the field of (V.A. Bakeev, V.F. Safin).

Let's dwell on a brief description of each of the listed directions. Relaxation therapy at the Pedagogical Department of the Perm State Pedagogical Institute (laboratory by I.E.Schwartz); The problem of pedagogical suggestopedia was considered by scientists in the context of intensification of the educational process through targeted pedagogical influence on the unconscious sphere of the psyche.

The result of the long-term work of a group of scientists proved the need to use

suggestopedia along with other methods of pedagogical influence, and the scope and features of its use were determined. The main focus was on the development of relaxation therapy technology and its use in the pedagogical process. I.E.Schwartz calls relaxationpedia one of the types of pedagogical influence, in which the state of relaxation serves as the basis for further absorbing influence for educational and educational purposes. Easing is characterized by a significant increase in the active self-suggestopedic skills and self-suggestopedic skills of the future educator, which differs from self-relaxation to various pedagogical suggestopedias. allows you to use it as a special launching pad. Relaxopedia can be individual and group. The results obtained at the end of this work served as a basis for further research.

Scientists of the Suggestopedia laboratory studied a wide range of problems. The possibility of using the influence of suggestopedia was studied during the training process (V.F. Kalugina, M.S. Pechersky, L.N. Tregubova). The possibilities of using relaxopedia in the educational process of higher educational institutions were considered (A.V. Malkova, N.V. Pystina, Z.A. Cherepanova). The method of using suggestopedia as a means of educational influence on children neglected by pedagogical attention (N.V. Blanova, A.S. Novoselova, V.I. Shkinder) has been developed.

The main conclusions of these studies are as follows.

- the most effective use of the method of pedagogical recommendations in working with future educators is to rely on his interest in a specific, direct professional activity. At a certain stage, this method can be the leader, but, of course, in combination with traditional methods of pedagogical influence.

- the method of pedagogical suggestopedia in the state of relaxation is one of the means of reducing the excessive impulsiveness of future teachers' behavior in the classroom.

The greater the student's cognitive level, the lower his cognitive activity, the lower the level of suggestopedic skills, the more cognitive activity he shows. It is possible to reduce the level of suggestopedic skills with the help of cognitive tasks that contribute to the elimination of stereotypes of skills.

- Relaxopedic training effectively helps weak students in mastering the vocabulary of a foreign language. Relaxed learning allows you to learn more words and phrases.

- It is necessary to actively use suggestopedia as an effective tool of pedagogical influence in the education of the sense of color in kindergarten children.

- The use of functional music (that is, music that plays in the background during the lesson) has an absorbing effect. Music affects emotions, the emotional sphere of a person, the subconscious and creates a certain mood. This emotional state inspired by music helps kindergarten children to focus and be attentive. Creative works performed to the accompaniment of music are characterized by more brightness and emotionality.

- The penetrating effect of the psyche of difficult children on the unconscious can be used for educational purposes. Recommended relations in a state of relaxation arouse positive aspirations in a teenager, give impetus and impetus to action. In the presence of the created conditions, the suggestopedia attitude is partially or completely implemented, and then (under the influence of the organized educational system) it can become a moral motive that determines all the behavior of the teenager.

Despite the importance of the work carried out by a large group of scientists, relaxation meopedia as one of the types of suggestopedia is not widely spread in the daily life of preschool

education organization. This can be explained by various reasons. First, the head of the laboratory I.E. Schwartz himself notes that it is limited in practice (for example, in relation to children who are difficult to understand). Secondly, the methodology requires a lot of time (specially organized classes, both individual and group), which is almost impossible in today's preschool education organization with a large workload of the teacher. Thirdly, the use of relaxation therapy requires serious psychological training, special knowledge and skills, which was very difficult in the 1970s and 1980s, and only in the last decade, the rapid development and organization of the Institute of Preschool Educational Psychologists in our country made possible by

For our research, G.A.Kovalev in the field of affective psychology, in particular, he examines suggestopedia and its potential for educational and especially re-educational purposes. Noting the controversial nature of the issue, G.A.Kovalev admits that the opinions of supporters and opponents of suggestopedia contain rational grains. The author's position on this issue is as follows: suggestopedia cannot be considered absolute, he considers it the main method of education and upbringing. At the same time, this means of influence cannot be discounted. "It affects an effective person and should be used in a system of various pedagogical tools, taking into account the age and psychophysical characteristics of future educators, and finally, the goals and tasks of education and training".

The author studied the possibilities of using the "absorption-suggestopedia" method for the purpose of re-education. According to this methodology, at the initial stage of re-education, the student's personality, family and class status, attitude towards the teacher and peers, his skills, real behavior and activities are thoroughly studied.

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